

Circuit Diagram :

Discussion

In the above experiment, it is clear that the ligands are different in their capacity of "spin pairing" or producing low-spin complexes from high spin central metal ions. The central atoms Mn^{2+} (5 unpaired electrons, d^5), Fe^{3+} (5 unpaired electrons, d^5) and Co^{3+} (4 unpaired electrons d^6) are all highly paramagnetic ions. But the results of magnetoelectrophoresis show that all their cyano-complexes are weakly paramagnetic. Thus CN^- is a very strong-field ligand. On the other hand, the fluoro-complexes are highly paramagnetic. Hence F^- is a weak field ligand. From the nature of the curves obtained⁺⁺ by plotting the data from the Table, it is possible to write the ligands with respect to their ligand-field strength, the following sequence:-

In the graph, distance migrated is plotted against field strength, from the slope of the curve, the paramagnetism of the complex is indicated, i.e., greater the slope, more is the paramagnetism, i.e., less is the ligand field. So, the order of the ligand field will be the reverse of the slope.

Reference

1. H. G. MUKHERJEE and D. MAJUMDAR, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1975, 277, 205.

Addition Complexes of Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) Haloacetates with Nitrogen Donors

N. KUMAR and A. K. GANDOTRA

Department of Chemistry, University of Jammu,
Jammu-180 001, India

Manuscript received 6 June 1978, revised 16 July 1979,
accepted 19 May 1980

THIS is in continuation to our work on complexes of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) carboxylates with pyridine type bases¹⁻³ and we wish to report now

preparation and characterisation of a number of complexes of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) haloacetates with heterocyclic ligands pyridine (Py), 2-, 3- and 4-methylpyridine (2-, 3-, 4-MePy), quinoline(Q) and isoquinoline(IQ) with a view to investigate their structure.

Experimental

Cobalt(II) and nickel(II) haloacetates were generated in solution by the interaction of the appropriate haloacetic acid with an excess of the required basic metal carbonate in ethanol under reflux and filtering off the excess of the unreacted metal carbonate. However, dichloroacetates of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) were isolated as solid samples by concentration of the filtrate obtained as described above. The initial crude products were recrystallised from methanol and dried in vacuum over phosphorus pentoxide. Their purity was established by metal analysis. Heterocyclic ligands were purified by fractional distillation over potassium hydroxide before use.

Preparation of Complexes: Complexes of mono- and trihaloacetates were prepared by the direct addition of the ligand in 1:2 molar ratio to the appropriate metal(II) haloacetate generated in ethanol. The reaction mixture on concentration and crystallisation invariably gave a solid crystalline product which was separated, washed with the appropriate solvent and dried in vacuum over phosphorous pentoxide.

Complexes of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) dichloroacetates were prepared by mixing the reactants in 1:2 or 1:4 metal to ligand ratios in acetone medium and working up the reaction mixture as described above.

Cobalt and nickel were estimated gravimetrically as tetrapyridinedithiocyanatocobalt(II) and bis(dimethylglyoximate)-nickel(II) respectively. Carbon and hydrogen contents of the samples were estimated in the micro-analytical laboratory of this department. Conductance measurements were carried on millimolar solutions in acetone using a Toshniwal Conductivity Bridge type CL 01/0,2A. Molecular weights were determined cryoscopically in nitrobenzene. Magnetic moments were determined by Gouy's method. Electronic spectra were recorded in chloroform on Beckman-DB-Spectrophotometer over the range 28,500-12,500 cm^{-1} . Infrared spectra were recorded in Nujol mulls on a Perkin-Elmer Infrared Spectrophotometer Model 621.

The analytical results, magnetic moments, conductivity and molecular weights wherever recorded are cited in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Analytical results show that the complexes formed are either of 1:2 or 1:4 stoichiometry.

TABLE 1—MAGNETIC, CONDUCTANCE, ANALYTICAL AND MOLECULAR WEIGHT DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Sl. No.	Compound	Colour	μ_{eff} B.M.	Conductance mole ⁻¹ ohm ⁻¹ cm ²	Metal(%)		Carbon(%)		Hydrogen(%)		Molecular weight	
					Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1.	Co(O ₂ CCH ₂ Cl) ₂ (2-MePy) ₂	Pink	5.02	4.32	13.76	13.95	44.34	44.43	4.03	4.15		
2.	Co(O ₂ CCH ₂ Cl) ₂ (Q) ₂	Pink	4.95	4.74	11.57	11.74	52.03	52.36	3.22	3.56		
3.	Co(O ₂ CCHCl ₂) ₂ (3-MePy) ₂	Pink	5.07	4.92	11.38	11.76	38.12	38.32	3.31	3.19	578	501
4.	Co(O ₂ CCHCl ₂) ₂ (4-MePy) ₂	Pink	5.05	5.05	11.45	11.76	38.18	38.32	3.12	3.19		
5.	Co(O ₂ CCHCl ₂) ₂ (IQ) ₂	Pink	5.05	4.92	10.13	10.28	45.85	46.39	2.70	2.82	530	573
6.	Co(O ₂ CCHCl ₂) ₂ (3-MePy) ₄	Red	5.02	4.34	8.34	8.57	49.00	48.87	3.95	4.35	508	687
7.	Co(O ₂ CCHCl ₂) ₂ (4-MePy) ₄	Red	4.96	5.98	8.49	8.57	48.34	48.87	4.07	4.35		
8.	Co(O ₂ CCHCl ₂) ₂ (IQ) ₄	Red	4.95	4.87	7.01	7.09	58.00	57.74	3.45	3.61	602	831
9.	Co(O ₂ CCl ₃) ₂ (4-MePy) ₂	Pink	5.03	10.82	10.21	10.34	33.51	33.70	2.16	2.45		
10.	Co(O ₂ CCF ₃) ₂ (IQ) ₂	Pink	4.96	17.32	10.53	10.87	—	48.73	—	2.58		
11.	Ni(O ₂ CCH ₂ Cl) ₂ (Py) ₂	Light blue	3.15	4.52	14.27	14.53	41.42	41.59	3.22	3.45		
12.	Ni(O ₂ CCHCl ₂) ₂ (3-MePy) ₂	Light blue	3.19	5.08	11.55	11.70	38.21	38.34	3.20	3.19		
13.	Ni(O ₂ CCHCl ₂) ₂ (4-MePy) ₂	Light blue	3.16	7.27	11.52	11.70	38.18	38.34	3.07	3.19	464	501
14.	Ni(O ₂ CCHCl ₂) ₂ (IQ) ₂	Light blue	3.20	8.78	10.02	10.26	46.25	46.42	2.66	2.81	591	642
15.	Ni(O ₂ CCHCl ₂) ₂ (3-MePy) ₄	Blue	3.16	4.32	8.36	8.55	48.71	48.88	4.23	4.35		
16.	Ni(O ₂ CCHCl ₂) ₂ (4-MePy) ₄	Blue	3.20	5.85	8.28	8.55	48.68	48.88	4.27	4.35	527	687
17.	Ni(O ₂ CCHCl ₂) ₂ (IQ) ₄	Blue	3.20	7.04	6.93	7.07	57.3	57.76	3.38	3.61	598	831
18.	Ni(O ₂ CCl ₃) ₂ (4-MePy) ₂	Light blue	3.20	12.78	10.15	10.30	33.53	33.72	2.31	2.45		
19.	Ni(O ₂ CCF ₃) ₂ (IQ) ₂	Light blue	3.22	18.52	10.68	10.75	—	48.73	—	2.58		

1 : 2 complexes are formed by all the metal(II) haloacetates but 1 : 4 complexes are formed by dichloroacetates of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) only. All the complexes are coloured and dissolve in common organic solvents giving stable solutions except those of 1 : 4 complexes which break up in solution to corresponding 1 : 2 complexes. Their conductance values (Table 1) indicate that complexes are non ionic⁴. Molecular weight studies on *bis*-amine complexes show them to be monomeric in solution. Magnetic moments of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes fall in the range of 4.95-5.07 and 3.15-3.22 B. M. respectively suggesting that the complexes are of high-spin octahedral configuration.

In their electronic spectra cobalt complexes show a strong band around 19,500 cm⁻¹ along with a shoulder around 20,500 cm⁻¹. The strong band like various other octahedral cobalt(II) complexes is assigned to ⁴T_{1g} → ⁴T_{1g} (P) transition and the shoulder may be observed to arise from the splitting of the visible band on account of spin-orbit coupling and/or the presence of quartet-doublet transitions⁵. The low value of molar extinction coefficient (Ca.30 l. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹) of these complexes further suggest that they have a transoctahedral configuration⁶. Complexes of nickel(II) carboxylates show two bands of low intensity (ε 10 l. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹) in the regions 15,740-15,900 and 26,000-27,300 cm⁻¹ and are assigned to ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g} and ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g} (P) transitions respectively pointing octahedral disposition of the complexes⁶.

Infrared spectra of all the complexes show a positive shift in almost all the frequencies originating from the ligand suggesting that the pyridine ligand coordinates through its nitrogen atom⁷. The frequency difference, Δ, between the asymmetric and symmetric stretching frequencies of the carboxylate group in the 1 : 2 complexes of metal(II) mono, di,

tri-chloro and trifluoroacetates lie in the range 250-255, 280-295, 335-350 and 315-325 cm⁻¹ respectively which are in close agreement to the Δ values observed in corresponding *bis*-amine complexes of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) haloacetates with pyridine⁸ indicating that the complexes are octahedral and haloacetate group is coordinated as a bidentate chelating ligand. This is further supported by C-F stretching frequencies which appear at 1200 and 1130 cm⁻¹ in cobalt trifluoroacetate complex and at 1170 and 1125 cm⁻¹ in nickel trifluoroacetate complex⁹. In 1 : 4 complexes Δ values lie in the range of 315-325 cm⁻¹ which show that the complexes under study are octahedral in which dichloroacetate group functions as a monodentate ligand⁸.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Professor O. P. Vig, Head, Department of Chemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh for providing facilities to carry out physical studies on these complexes.

References

1. B. S. MANHAS, G. S. JOLLY, N. KUMAR and A. K. GANDOTRA, *J. Chem. Sci.*, 1975, **1**, 1; *Chem. Abs.*, 1976, **85**, 153240h.
2. N. KUMAR and A. K. GANDOTRA, *Acta Ciencia, Indica*, 1977, **3**, 198.
3. N. KUMAR and A. K. GANDOTRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 535.
4. R. S. NYHOLM, R. G. CUNNINGHAM and M. L. TOBE, *J. Chem. Soc. Dalton*, 1972, 229.
5. A. B. P. LEVER, 'Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy', Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.
6. F. A. COTTON, D. M. GOODGAME and R. H. SODERBERG, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, **2**, 1162.
7. N. N. GREENWOOD and K. WADE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 1130.

8. A. B. P. LEVER and D. OGDEN, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1967, 2041.
 9. C. A. AGAMBAR, P. ANASTREY and K. G. ORRELL, *J. Chem. Soc. Dalton*, 1974, 964.

Studies in Fe(III) 6, 7-Dihydroxy-Naphthalene-2-Sulphonic Acid Complexes

M. L. NARWADE, S. W. SATHE and M. V. KARBELKAR

Department of Chemistry, Vidarbha Mahavidyalaya,
Amaravati

Manuscript received 2 November 1977, revised 24 April 1979,
accepted 19 May 1980

SULPHONIC acids are known to form coloured complexes with Fe(III). Mc.Bryde⁸ has studied Fe(III) complexes of 8-hydroxyquinoline-7-sulphonic acid spectrophotometrically. Recently Narwade⁹ has investigated the interaction of transitional metal ions with sulphonic acids.

A preliminary experiment with solutions containing Fe(III) perchlorate ($1 \times 10^{-2} M$) and sodium salt of 6-7 dihydroxy-naphthalene-2-sulphonic acid (6, 7 DHN-2SA), ($20 \times 10^{-2} M$) and free $HClO_4$ showed colour change from dark-blue, violet and then to orange when pH was varied from 2 to 8. This indicated the presence of more than one complex species in solution. A potentiometric study was undertaken to determine the stability constants of complexes of Fe(III) with 6, 7 DHN-2SA. Spectrophotometric study was made with a limited aim to confirm the result of potentiometry.

Experimental

Potentiometry: The experimental procedure involved the Calvin-Bjerrum titrations of three carbonate-free mixtures: (1) Free $HClO_4$ ($1.002 \times 10^{-2} M$), (2) Free $HClO_4$ (1.002×10^{-2}) + 6, 7 DHN-2SA ($20.0 \times 10^{-4} M$) and (3) Free $HClO_4$ ($1.002 \times 10^{-2} M$) + 6, 7 DHN-2SA + Ferric perchlorate ($4.0 \times 10^{-4} M$). All the mixtures were titrated separately with 0.1818M NaOH solution in a double walled titration vessel with a seal on water jacket at a temperature of $25 \pm 0.2^\circ$. Total volume was 50 ml each time. The ionic strength of 0.1M was maintained constant by adding $NaClO_4$ solution. The titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere by bubbling oxygen free nitrogen gas through the assembly containing the electrodes in order to exclude CO_2 .

pH measurements were made with a ELICO pH Meter (accuracy ± 0.05 unit) using glass and calomel electrodes.

From the shifts in the pH titration curves the values of \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and pL , were calculated by Irving and Rossotti's method.

Results and Discussion

The acid+ligand curve was found to be coinciding with the acid curve upto pH 6.0 (Fig. 1). This was expected as the ligand 6, 7 DHN-2SA was taken in the form of its sodium salt. In water, the salt dissociates into sodium ion and ionic ligand (H_2L^-). The sulphonic acid is a good chelating agent and is highly acidic due to its $-SO_3H$ group. The dissociation equilibria can be represented as under:

From the plot of \bar{n}_A vs pH (Fig. 1a) pK values were determined. The pK_1 (first dissociation constant of $-OH$ group) at $\bar{n}_A=1.5$, which was found 8.10, be ascribed to the $-OH$ group in the 6th position,

Fig. 1(a)

because the overall electron withdrawing effect of the $-SO_3^-$ group is efficiently transferred to the 6-hydroxy group. The hydrogen bonding between the pentoxide ion of 6th position and the $-OH$ group at the 7th position would increase the dissociation constant of the $-OH$ group in 7th position leading to a higher value of pK_2 (second dissociation constant of $-OH$ group). The accurate pK_2 value could not be determined due to the limited accuracy of glass electrode above pH 11.0. Actual titrations are carried out above pH 12.0. The value of pK_2 corresponding to the pH, where $\bar{n}_A=0.5$